

Development and Numerical Simulations of a Mathematical Model of the Hepatitis B Virus Transmission Dynamics and Control in Nigeria

Muhammad Audu Shuaibu ✉
Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

Martha Haruna
Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

Ummulkhair Aliyu Buhari
Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

Article History:

Received: 08.01.2025 Revised: 31.01.2025 Accepted: 20.02.2025 Published: 22.02.2025

Abstract

In the work, we developed and numerically simulate a mathematical model for the transmission dynamics and control of hepatitis B virus (HBV) in Nigeria, incorporating faithfulness, condom usage and treatment. Numerical simulations revealed that faithfulness for sexually active individuals is the best strategy that can be used to control the transmission of HBV, it is better to remain faithful than to use condom. Thus, we recommend that all sexually active individuals in Nigeria should remain faithful.

Keywords: *Hepatitis B virus (HBV), Control measures, Faithfulness, Deterministic model, Transmission dynamics.*

Suggested citation: Shuaibu, M.A., Haruna, M., & Buhari, U.A. (2025). Development and Numerical Simulations of a Mathematical Model of the Hepatitis B Virus Transmission Dynamics and Control in Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(2), 52-61. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(2\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(2).04)

Introduction

Hepatitis B is a potentially life-threatening liver infection caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV). HBV is a DNA virus classified in the virus family of Hepadnaviridae. HBV infection is a significant public health problem in Nigeria, with an estimated 20 million people infected and a prevalence rate of 11% among adults. The virus is transmitted through exposure to infected blood and bodily fluids, and can lead to serious health consequences such as liver cancer, cirrhosis, and liver failure. Despite the

availability of an effective vaccine and antiviral treatments, the burden of HBV infection in Nigeria remains high, particularly in vulnerable populations such as infants, young children, and people living with HIV (Halfmann *et al.*, 2020). Hepatitis B is one of the world's most serious health problems. More than a billion people around the world have serological indicators of past or present infection with hepatitis B virus (HBV). Over 300 million people are chronic carriers of the virus (Onuzulike and Ogueri, 2007). HBV infection can be transmitted from

mother to child (vertical), contact with an infected person (horizontal transmission), sexual contact (homosexual and heterosexual transmission) with infected partners, exposure to blood or other infected fluids and contact with HBV contaminated instruments (WHO, 2002).

Hepatitis B was called serum hepatitis in the past. This virus has a number of serological types and the infection occurs at any age but mostly in adults. The incubation period is 50 to 180 days. The virus enters the blood and is spread by blood and blood products. Antibodies are formed and immunity persists after recovery. Infection usually leads to severe illness lasting 2 to 3 weeks, often followed by a protracted convalescence. Carriers may or may not have had clinical disease. Type B virus (serum hepatitis) may cause massive liver necrosis and death and in less severe cases recovery may be complete. In chronic hepatitis which may develop, live virus continues to circulate in the blood and other body fluids, that is, saliva, semen, vaginal secretions. The condition may predispose to liver cancer. Hepatitis is the inflammation of the liver caused by virus, toxic substances or immunological abnormalities. Infectious hepatitis is caused by viruses, several types of which have been isolated as specific causes of the disease and can be detected by tests. Associated with acute viral hepatitis is acute infection with hepatitis B virus and it starts with general ill – health such as mild fever, dark urine, nausea, loss of appetite, vomiting, body aches, and then progress to development of jaundice. The illness lasts for few weeks before gradually improves in most effected people. Few patients may die as a result of fulminant hepatic failure and in some individuals, the infection may go unrecognized (asymptomatic) (Zeng *et al.*, 2021). Chronic HBV may be either asymptomatic or associated with a chronic inflammation of the liver, leading to cirrhosis over a period of several years. Incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma (liver cancer) increases in chronic HBV patients. Avoidance of alcohol consumption is recommended to chronic carriers of HBV infection because it increases their risk for cirrhosis and liver cancer. Hepatitis B virus has been linked to the development of

membranous glomerulonephritis (MGN) (Chang, 2007).

Despite efforts by the Nigerian government and international organizations to reduce the burden of HBV infection in the country, progress has been slow due to a range of challenges, including inadequate funding, limited healthcare resources, and a lack of data on the epidemiology of the virus. There is a need for more research on the dynamics of HBV transmission in Nigeria and the most effective strategies for controlling its spread (Zou *et al.*, 2022).

The development of a mathematical model of HBV transmission dynamics and control in Nigeria can provide important insights into the factors that contribute to the spread of the virus and the most effective strategies for preventing its transmission. Mathematical model is a powerful tool that can help predict the trajectory of an epidemic, evaluate the impact of different control measures, and inform policy decisions on disease control. In the case of HBV, mathematical models can help to identify the key factors that contribute to its transmission and to evaluate the potential impact of interventions such as vaccination programs and improved healthcare facilities. This project aims to develop a mathematical model of HBV transmission dynamics in Nigeria and to use it to evaluate the effectiveness of various control measures.

There is a need for more research on the dynamics of HBV transmission in Nigeria and the most effective strategies for controlling its spread. While previous studies have provided important insights into the epidemiology of HBV in Nigeria, there is still much that is not understood about the complex interplay of factors that contribute to the transmission of the virus (Zhang and Zhou, 2021).

The development of a mathematical model of HBV transmission dynamics and control in Nigeria is particularly important given the high burden of HBV infection in the country and the limited resources available for disease control. Mathematical model can help identify the most effective control measures for reducing the spread of HBV and provide guidance on how to allocate resources for disease control (Pang *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, the development of a mathematical model can help build the capacity of local researchers and public health professionals in the use of mathematical model for infectious disease control. This can enhance the ability of Nigeria to conduct research on infectious diseases and develop evidence-based interventions for disease control, leading to improved health outcomes, reduced healthcare costs, and increased productivity (Khan *et al.*, 2020).

Materials and Methods

A mathematical model of hepatitis B virus HBV, was developed as a disease to understand the transmission dynamics and control of HBV. We consider the Adult population. The total population $N(t)$ is subdivided into five (5) compartments of the Susceptible individuals $S(t)$, Faithful individuals $F(t)$, Acute individuals $A(t)$, Chronic individuals $C(t)$ and Recovered individuals $R(t)$. Susceptible is an individual that is yet to be infected, but is open to infection as he or she get in contact with members of the infected class. A faithful individual is the one who abstain from any form of contact with the affected individuals in the population, or having a mutually monogamous relationship with an uninfected partner. Faithfulness is a strategy that can be used to prevent the transmission of HBV. This means that the effective transmission rate of HBV can be reduced by the factor faithfulness. Acute individual is one who has just contracted HBV. Chronic is an individual who is HBV positive, but has progressed from acute to a very severe stage of infection.

Lastly, a recovered individual is one that is confirmed to be HBV negative.

In the construction of the model some of the following assumptions are taken in to consideration:

That the population is heterogeneous, hence, the individuals that make up the population can be grouped into different compartments or classes according to their epidemiological state.

1. The Adult population was considered.

2. That the population size in a compartment is differentiable with respect to time and the epidemic process is deterministic.

3. That the population mixes homogeneously. That is all susceptible individuals are equally likely to be infected by infectious individuals in case of contact.

4. That people in each compartment have equal natural death rate μ .

5. Faithfulness, effective compliance to the use of condom, treatment as the control measures.

6. Faithfulness as the best means of control.

7. We denote the classes S , A , C and R in the population respectively by differentiating the compartment using ordinary differential equation.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of HBV Transmission and Control Model

The $S(t)$ sub-population is generated from daily recruitment of HBV uninfected individuals at the rate λ . They acquired infection and move to the $A(t)$ class via sexual transmission given by $\frac{\beta(A+C)(1-\epsilon)cS}{N}$. The parameter β is the effective sexual contact rate. The term $(1 - \epsilon c)$ reflect the impact of condom usage which is enhanced by compliance on sexual transmission, $0 < \epsilon, c < 1$. The compartment decreases due to those leaving the compartment to the acute individual and natural death. $A(t)$ is generated

through effective contact between the susceptible individuals and the infectious individuals given by the term $\frac{\beta(A+C)(1-\varepsilon c)S}{N}$ as earlier discussed the compartment decrease by natural death, disease induced death and by the recovered individuals at the rates $\mu + \delta_1$ and $\sigma\gamma$ respectively. Similarly, the $C(t)$ compartment is generated by those leaving the acute individuals to the chronic compartment at the rate of $\sigma(1 - \gamma)$, than the compartment decreases due to those recovering due to treatment, and reduces by natural death and disease induced death at the rate of $\mu + \delta_2$ and $\tau.R(t)$ compartment is generated from both individuals the acute and chronic compartment at the rate of τ and $\sigma\gamma$. Similarly $F(t)$ compartment is generated by the rate of f indicate the which susceptible individuals becomes faithful and reduced by natural death μ .

The corresponding mathematical equations of the schematic diagram can be described by a system of ordinary differential equations given below:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \Lambda - \frac{\beta(A+C)(1-\varepsilon c)S}{N} - (f + \mu)S \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dF}{dt} = fS - \mu F \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{\beta(A+C)(1-\varepsilon c)S}{N} - \sigma A - (\mu + \delta_1)A \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \sigma(1 - \gamma)A + \tau C - (\mu + \delta_2)C \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \sigma\gamma A + \tau C - \mu R \quad (5)$$

Where:

$$N(t) = S(t) + F(t) + A(t) + C(t) + R(t)$$

So that,

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \Lambda - \mu N - \delta_1 A - \delta_2 C$$

Results and Discussion

The exact values of the variable are hard to get, most of the variables are assumed except the total population that was gotten from the World Population Dashboard Nigeria given in the table below.

Table 1. Values for Variables of the Model

S\N	Variable	Value	Source
1	N	117180000	WPDN(2022)
2	S	97180000	Fitted
3	F	1000000	Fitted
4	A	10000000	Fitted
5	C	3000000	Fitted
6	R	6000000	Fitted

The exact values of the parameter are gotten from two different source Nigerian Bureau of Statistics and Abdulrahman, (2013), given in the table below:

Table 2. Values for Parameters of the Model

S\N	Parameter	Values	Source
1	Λ	2,109,240	NBS(2022)
2	μ	0.018	NBS(2022)
3	β	0.9	Abdulrahman, (2013)
4	σ	2.668	Abdulrahman, (2013)
5	γ	0.9	Abdulrahman, (2013)
6	δ_1	0.007	Abdulrahman, (2013)
7	δ_2	0.001	Abdulrahman, (2013)
8	τ	0.1	Control Parameter
9	ε	0.1	Control Parameter
10	f	0.1	Control Parameter
11	c	0.1	Control Parameter

The numerical simulations for the model system under various conditions are presented in this

section. Using the variable and parameter values provided above, we compute our model using maple; software to run the simulations, we were able to produce the graphs below:

Figure 2. The Effect of Zero Control Measures on Faithfulness, Treatment and Effective Compliance to the Use of Condoms

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023

It was observed from the figure 2 above that if there is no control measure the Morbidity of Infected Individuals increase with a high rate. This shows that there is need for control measures on the infected individuals to reduce morbidity of infection, if there is no any control measures, the disease may affect the total population which may lead to endemic.

At 0.0 level of intervention the disease keep decrease with respect to time while at 0.25 and 0.50 individuals decreases almost at the same level of control with a high speed, at 0.75, the effect on morbidity of infected individuals decreases completely. From the graph above it's also observed that the acute individuals at 0.00,0.025,0.50 and 0.05 decreases even without control, this is because at acute stage of infection, the adult immune system fight the virus naturally within six month of infection.

Hence the rate of recovery is high at acute stage (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Comparison between the Effect of No, Low, Moderate and High Treatment on Morbidity of Acute Infected Individuals
Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023

Figure 4. Comparison between the Effect of No, Low, Moderate and High Treatment on Morbidity of Chronic Infected Individuals. Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

From figure 4 above, it show that the rate at which chronic infected individuals with no low, moderate and high control parameters decreases with respect to time unlike the acute individuals. Chronic individuals respond slowly to the control measures. At 0.00 the disease increasing with respect to time, at 0.25 the disease reduces far better than 0.00 while at 0.50 and 0.75 the disease decrease with a low speed unlike the acute individuals.

Figure 5. Comparison between the Effect of No, Low, Moderate and High Faithfulness on Morbidity of Infected Individuals

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

From figure 5 above, the graph shows that as 0.00 faithfulness acute individuals increases in number with respect to time but at 0.5 decreases more than 0.00, at a high rate of control 0.75 the disease decreases with a high speed and dies up completely with respect to time.

From figure 6 above, it shows that acute individuals keep recovery naturally even at a low level of control. The adult population recover naturally. At 0.00 of compliance the affected individuals decrease with respect to time, at 0.25 the rate at which the infected individuals recover differs better than compliance at 0.00 with respect to time, while at 0.50 of compliance the morbidity of acute infections individuals reduces with a high speed.

Figure 6. Comparison between the Effect of No, Low and High Compliance of Condom Usage on Morbidity of Acute Infected Individuals

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

Figure 7. Comparison between the Effect of No, Low, Moderate and High Compliance of Condom Usage on Morbidity of Chronic Infected Individuals

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

From figure 7 above, the effect of compliance of condom usage on Morbidity of chronic Infected Individuals has effect both on low at 0.00, 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75. at 0.00 the disease increases at 0.25 the disease decrease with a low rate while at 0.75 the disease reduces with a high speed. If there is 0.75 effective compliance to the usage of condom the morbidity of hepatitis B will die off on sexually active individuals.

Figure 8. Comparison between the Effect of Low Rate of Faithfulness and High Effective Compliance to the Use of Condom on Acute Infected Individuals
Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

From figure 8 above, the effect of moderate control measure of faithfulness on morbidity of infected individuals has more effect than 0.75 compliance to the use of condom. It's observed that if individuals will have a low rate of faithfulness the morbidity of infected individual will reduce with respect to time. Faithfulness is far better than compliance to be used of condom, at 0.75 because if there is compliance without 100% effectiveness to be used of condom the morbidity will increase with respect to time.

Figure 9. Comparison between the Effect of Low Rate of Faithfulness and High Effective Compliance to the Use of Condom on Chronic Infected Individuals
Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

From figure 9 above, the graph shows that even at low rate of faithfulness the morbidity on the infected individuals reduces in a slow rate while effective use of condoms with compliance 0.75 reduces with respect to time. It's observed that faithfulness and compliance to the effective use of condom a good control measures on sexually actives individuals.

From figure 10 above, at 0.75 treatment the graph decreases slowly but at 0.75 faithfulness the effect on morbidity of infected individuals reduces drastically. This shows that both faithfulness and treatment has effect on morbidity of the infected individuals but differs with time. Faithfulness has more effect than treatment, if individuals will remain faithful from the susceptible.

From figure 11 above, the graph shows the effect of high rate of control measures with respect to time. At 0.75. at 0.75 treatment the disease reduces slowly at 0.75 of faithfulness the disease reduces drastically, while at 0.75 compliance the disease reduces slowly with respect to time this shows that faithfulness has

more effect on the control measures it's better to remain faithful than to use condom.

Figure 10. Comparison between High Rate of Faithfulness and High Rate of Treatment on Infected Individuals

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

Figure 11. Comparison between High Rate of Faithfulness, High Rate of Treatment and High Rate of Effective Compliance to the Use of Condom on Infected Individuals

Source: Author's own computation using Maple, May, 2023.

Conclusion

Hepatitis B virus is a potentially life threatening liver infection caused by the hepatitis B virus HBV. Faithfulness is acknowledged as the best method to control the disease, a mathematical model was developed, with consideration of different compartments of individuals namely:(susceptible, acute, chronic and recovered compartments) for the model equations, Numerical simulations of the was obtained using maple software.

Furthermore, our simulation reveals that effective use of condom, treatment, faithfulness has effect on the morbidity of infectious individuals. Hence it reveals faithfulness as the most effective control measure.

Recommendation

Hepatitis B virus is highly prevalent and control of HB is a major public health concern in Nigeria. Considering the finding of the study, we suggest the following strategies, if successfully used, will serve as the gateway in controlling hepatitis B virus in Nigeria;

1. Educate the public: there is a need to educate the public by sharing the findings about the disease, especially those at risk of contracting Hepatitis B virus. It is also believed that random sexual affairs help in spreading the disease, hence it's important to educate the public on the effectiveness of faithfulness as a control measure and encourage them to consider this option.
2. Provision of counseling and support: For individuals who choose to adopt faithfulness as a control measure, it may be helpful to provide counseling and support to help them maintain their commitment. This can include providing resources for healthy communication in relationships and strategies for building trust.
3. Healthcare providers can play an important role in promoting faithfulness as a control measure and helping patients understand their options. Consider collaborating with healthcare providers to share findings and develop resources for patients.

Raising awareness of Hepatitis B virus: Hepatitis B virus is a serious health issue that affects millions of people worldwide. Raising awareness

of this issue and promoting prevention strategies beyond just faithfulness and condom usage can play a vital role in curtailing the virus. This can include vaccination, regular testing, and access to healthcare resources.

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